

Using Ergodic Theory to understand Combinatorics: The case of Pythagorean Pairs

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- 5 Open Problems and Future work

Historical Context

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Some famous example of Diophantine Equation:

① $ax + by = c$

② $w^3 + x^3 = y^3 + z^3$

③ $x^n + y^n = z^n$

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- In 2006, Khalfalah proved the PR of $x + y = z^2$ if we allow z to not share color with x and y .
- In 2012, Csikvári showed that $x + y = z^2$ is not PR.
- In 2016 $x^2 + y^2 = z^2$ was prove to be PR restricted to 2-coloring's. ("longest mathematical proof")
- Finally, in 2023 N. Frantzikinakis, O. Klurman and J. Moreira proved the PR for $x^2 + y^2$ if we allow z to not share color with x and y ($ax^2 + by^2 = cz^2$ where a, b, c are squares).

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Roadmap to the proofs

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Theorem (1.1)

Let $a, b, c \in \mathbb{N}$ be squares. Then for every finite coloring of \mathbb{N} there exist

(i) distinct $x, y \in \mathbb{N}$ with the same color and $z \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $ax^2 + by^2 = cz^2$.

(ii) distinct $y, z \in \mathbb{N}$ with the same color and $x \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $ax^2 + by^2 = cz^2$.

Theorem (1.2)

Let $a, b, c \in \mathbb{N}$ be squares. Then for every $\Lambda \subset \mathbb{N}$ with positive multiplicative density, there exist

(i) distinct $x, y \in \Lambda$ and $z \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $ax^2 + by^2 = cz^2$.

(ii) distinct $y, z \in \Lambda$ and $x \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $ax^2 + by^2 = cz^2$.

Recall:

Definition (Upper density)

The upper density of a set $\Lambda \subset \mathbb{N}$ is defined by

$$\bar{d}(\Lambda) := \limsup_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|\Lambda \cap \{1, \dots, N\}|}{N}.$$

Roadmap to the proofs

Definition (Multiplicative Følner Sequence)

A Multiplicative Følner sequence in \mathbb{N} is a sequence $\Phi = (\Phi_K)_{K=1}^{\infty}$ of finite subsets of \mathbb{N} asymptotically invariant under dilation, in the sense that

$$\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|\Phi_K \cap (x \cdot \Phi_K)|}{|\Phi_K|} = 1 \quad \text{for all } x \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Definition (Additive Følner Sequence)

An Additive Følner sequence in \mathbb{N} is a sequence $\Phi = (\Phi_K)_{K=1}^{\infty}$ of finite subsets of \mathbb{N} asymptotically invariant under addition, in the sense that

$$\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|\Phi_K \cap (x + \Phi_K)|}{|\Phi_K|} = 1 \quad \text{for all } x \in \mathbb{N}.$$

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Definition (Upper multiplicative (additive) density)

The upper multiplicative (additive) density of a set $\Lambda \subset \mathbb{N}$ with respect to a multiplicative (additive) Følner sequence Φ is defined as

$$\bar{d}_{\Phi}(\Lambda) := \limsup_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|\Phi_K \cap \Lambda|}{|\Phi_K|}.$$

Roadmap to the proofs

Parametric solutions to $ax^2 + b^2 = cz^2$:

$$x = kl_1(m^2 - n^2), \quad y = kl_2mn, \quad z = kl_3(m^2 + n^2), \quad m, n \in \mathbb{N}$$

where $l_1 := a_0bc, l_2 := 2ab_0c, l_3 := abc_0$ and
 $a = a_0^2, b = b_0^2, c = c_0^2$ for $a_0, b_0, c_0 \in \mathbb{N}$

Theorem (1.3)

Suppose that $\Lambda \subset \mathbb{N}$ satisfies $\bar{d}_\Phi(\Lambda) > 0$ for some multiplicative Følner sequence Φ . Then for every $l, l' \in \mathbb{N}$ there exist

(i) $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$ with $m > n$ such that $l(m^2 - n^2)$ and $l'mn$ are distinct and

$$\bar{d}_\Phi((l(m^2 - n^2))^{-1}\Lambda \cap (l'mn)^{-1}\Lambda) > 0$$

(ii) $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $l(m^2 + n^2)$ and $l'mn$ are distinct and

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By the Furstenberg correspondence principle:

There exists a probability space, say (X, μ) and a measure preserving action, say $T = (T_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ on X and a measurable set $A \subset X$ with $\mu(A) = \bar{d}_\Phi(\Lambda) > 0$ and for any $g_1, \dots, g_k \in \mathbb{N}$ we have:

$$\mu(A \cap T_{g_1}^{-1}A \cap \dots \cap T_{g_k}^{-1}A) \leq \bar{d}_\Phi(\Lambda \cap (g_1^{-1}\Lambda) \cap \dots \cap (g_k^{-1}\Lambda))$$

Theorem (1.4)

Let $l, l' \in \mathbb{N}$, let $T = (T_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a measure preserving action of (\mathbb{N}, \times) on a probability space (X, μ) , and let $A \subset X$ be a measurable with $\mu(A) > 0$. Then there exist

(i) $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$ with $m > n$ such that $l(m^2 - n^2)$ and $l'mn$ are distinct and

$$\mu(T_{l(m^2-n^2)}^{-1}A \cap T_{l'mn}^{-1}A) > 0$$

(ii) $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $l(m^2 + n^2)$ and $l'mn$ are distinct and

$$\mu(T_{l(m^2+n^2)}^{-1}A \cap T_{l'mn}^{-1}A) > 0$$

By the theorem of Bochner-Herglotz:

There exists a finite Borel measure σ on \mathcal{M} such that $\sigma(\{1\}) > 0$ and for every $r, s \in \mathbb{N}$ we have

$$\int_{\mathcal{M}} f(r) \cdot \overline{f(s)} d\sigma(f) = \mu(T_r^{-1}A \cap T_s^{-1}A)$$

where

$$\mathcal{M} := \{f : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^1 \text{ is a completely multiplicative function} \}$$

Recall:

Definition (Completely multiplicative function)

A function $f : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^1$ is said to be a completely multiplicative function if

$$f(mn) = f(m) \cdot f(n), \quad \text{for all } m, n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

In order to understand better the set \mathcal{M} here are some examples of completely multiplicative function

- 1 $f(n) = n^{it}$
- 2 Liouville function
- 3 Dirichlet characters

Theorem (1.5)

Let σ be a positive bounded measure on \mathcal{M} such that $\sigma(\{1\}) > 0$ and

$$\int_{\mathcal{M}} f(r) \cdot \overline{f(s)} \, d\sigma(f) \geq 0 \text{ for every } r, s \in \mathbb{N}$$

Then for every $l, l' \in \mathbb{N}$ we have

(i)

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}_{m, n \in [N], m > n} \int_{\mathcal{M}} f(l(m^2 - n^2)) \cdot \overline{f(l'mn)} \, d\sigma(f) > 0$$

(ii)

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}_{m, n \in [N]} \int_{\mathcal{M}} f(l(m^2 + n^2)) \cdot \overline{f(l'mn)} \, d\sigma(f) > 0$$

Pythagorean Pairs I

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Pythagorean Pairs I

They proved Theorem 1.5 by taking an average over the grid

$$\{(Qm + 1, Qn) : m, n \in \mathbb{N}\}$$

Definition (2.1)

For $\delta > 0$, $f \in \mathcal{M}$, $Q, m, n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $l, l' \in \mathbb{N}$ fixed, let

$$A_\delta(f, Q; m, n) := w_\delta(m, n) \cdot f(l((Qm + 1)^2 - (Qn)^2)) \cdot \overline{f(l'(Qm + 1)Qn)}$$

Theorem (2.2)

Let σ be a Borel probability measure on \mathcal{M} such that $\sigma(\{1\}) > 0$. Then there exist $\delta_0 > 0$ and $Q_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ depending only on σ such that

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}_{m, n \in [N]} \int_{\mathcal{M}} A_{\delta_0}(f, Q_0; m, n) d\sigma(f) > 0$$

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Pythagorean Pairs I

Proposition (2.3)

Let $f : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{U}$ be an aperiodic completely multiplicative function. Then for every $\delta > 0$ and $Q \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}_{m, n \in [N]} A_\delta(f, Q; m, n) = 0.$$

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In order to prove Theorem 2.2 it suffices to show:

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}_{m,n \in [N]} \int_{\mathcal{M}} A_{\delta_0}(f, Q_0; m, n) d\sigma(f) > 0 \longrightarrow \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}_{m,n \in [N]} \int_{\mathcal{M}_p} A_{\delta_0}(f, Q_0; m, n) d\sigma(f) > 0$$

Lemma (2.4)

Let $f \in \mathcal{M}_p \setminus \mathcal{A}$, $\delta > 0$, $l, l' \in \mathbb{N}$ and Φ_K . Then

$$\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}_{Q \in \Phi_K} \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}_{m, n \in [N]} A_\delta(f, Q; m, n) = 0.$$

where

$$\Phi_K := \left\{ \prod_{p \leq K} p^{a_p} : K < a_p \leq 2K \right\} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{A} := \{(n^{it})_{n \in \mathbb{N}} : t \in \mathbb{R}\}.$$

Pythagorean Pairs I

Proposition (2.5)

Let $f : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{U}$ be a multiplicative function such that $f \sim \chi \cdot n^{it}$ for some $t \in \mathbb{R}$ and Dirichlet character χ with period q . Suppose that K is large enough so that q divides all elements of Φ_K . Then

$$\limsup_{N \rightarrow \infty} \max_{Q \in \Phi_K} \mathbb{E}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} |f(Qn + 1) - (Qn)^{it} \cdot \exp(F_N(f, K))| \ll \mathbb{D}(f, \chi \cdot n^{it}; K, \infty) + K^{-1/2}$$

where the implicit constant is absolute and

$$F_N(f, K) := \sum_{K < p \leq N} \frac{1}{p} (f(p) \cdot \overline{\chi(p)} \cdot p^{-it} - 1)$$

Lemma (2.6)

Let (Φ_K) be a multiplicative Følner sequence. If $f : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{U}$ is a completely multiplicative function and $f \neq 1$, then

$$\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}_{n \in \Phi_K} f(n) = 0,$$

Lemma (2.7)

Let σ be a Borel probability measure on \mathcal{M} such that $\sigma(\{1\}) > 0$. Then there exists $\delta_0, \rho_0 > 0$, depending only on σ , such that

$$\liminf_{N \rightarrow \infty} \inf_{Q \in \mathbb{N}} \mathfrak{R} \left(\mathbb{E}_{m, n \in [N]} \int_{\mathcal{A}} A_{\delta_0}(f, Q; m, n) d\sigma(f) \right) \geq \rho_0$$

By combining Proposition 2.3, Lemma 2.4 and Lemma 2.7, it can be concluded that Theorem 2.2 holds.

Recall:

Theorem (2.2)

Let σ be a Borel probability measure on \mathcal{M} such that $\sigma(\{1\}) > 0$. Then there exist $\delta_0 > 0$ and $Q_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ depending only on σ such that

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}_{m,n \in [N]} \int_{\mathcal{M}} A_{\delta_0}(f, Q_0; m, n) d\sigma(f) > 0$$

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Definition (3.1)

For $\delta > 0$, $f \in \mathcal{M}$, $Q, m, n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $l, l' \in \mathbb{N}$ fixed, let

$$B_\delta(f, Q; m, n) := \tilde{w}_\delta(m, n) \cdot f(l((Qm+1)^2 + (Qn)^2)) \cdot \overline{f(l'(Qm+1)Qn)}$$

Theorem (3.2)

Let σ be a Borel probability measure on \mathcal{M} such that $\sigma(\{1\}) > 0$.
Then there exist $\delta_0 > 0$ such that

$$\liminf_{N \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}_{m, n \in [N]} \int_{\mathcal{M}} B_{\delta_0}(f, 1; m, n) d\sigma(f) > 0$$

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Proposition (3.3)

Let $f : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{U}$ be an aperiodic completely multiplicative function. Then for every $\delta > 0$ and $Q \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}_{m,n \in [N]} B_\delta(f, Q; m, n) = 0.$$

Proposition (3.4)

Let (Φ_K) , \mathcal{A} , $B_\delta(f, Q; m, n)$ and $\delta > 0$. Let also σ be a Borel probability measure on \mathcal{M}_p . Then

$$\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \limsup_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left| \mathbb{E}_{Q \in \Phi_K} \mathbb{E}_{m, n \in [N]} \int_{\mathcal{M}_p \setminus \mathcal{A}} B_\delta(f, Q; m, n) d\sigma(f) \right| = 0.$$

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Let $f : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{U}$ be a multiplicative function such that $f \sim \chi \cdot n^{it}$ for some $t \in \mathbb{R}$ and Dirichlet character χ with period q . Suppose that K is large enough so that q divides all elements of Φ_K . Then

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Let σ be a Borel probability measure on \mathcal{M}_p such that $\sigma(\{1\}) > 0$. Then there exists $\delta_0, \rho_0 > 0$, depending only on σ , such that

$$\liminf_{N \rightarrow \infty} \inf_{Q \in \mathbb{N}} \mathfrak{R} \left(\mathbb{E}_{m, n \in [N]} \int_{\mathcal{A}} B_{\delta_0}(f, Q; m, n) d\sigma(f) \right) \geq \rho_0$$

Finally, By combining Proposition 3.3, Proposition 3.4 and Lemma 3.6, it can be concluded that Theorem 3.2 holds.

Recall:

Theorem (3.2)

Let σ be a Borel probability measure on \mathcal{M} such that $\sigma(\{1\}) > 0$. Then there exist $\delta_0 > 0$ and $Q_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ depending only on σ such that

$$\liminf_{N \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}_{m,n \in [N]} \int_{\mathcal{M}} B_{\delta_0}(f, 1; m, n) d\sigma(f) > 0$$

Open Problems and Future work

- 1 Historical Context
- 2 Roadmap to the proofs
- 3 Pythagorean Pairs I
- 4 Pythagorean Pairs II
- 5 Open Problems and Future work

Open problems:

- The case of PR for Pythagorean triples stills open
Some ideas to solve it:

- The authors proved that no "natural" counterexample can be find.
- Develop deeper the structure theory for (\mathbb{N}, \times) .
- Adapt/Develop the structure theory for (\mathbb{N}, \times) known to the specific equation $ax^2 + by^2 = cz^2$.

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Other open problems can be:

- Try other conditions on the coefficients a, b, c . Do not force that a, b, c are squares. For example:
Show PR for $x^2 + y^2 = 2z^2$, where x, y share the same color and $z \in \mathbb{N}$.
- Prove PR for more general forms. Such as

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Thank you!

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